

THE FAMILY IS THE SUPPORT OF THE STATE**Sultansaidova Saodat****Ph.D. of Philology, Associate Professor,****Uzbekistan State University of World Languages, holder of
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Abstract. In modern life, creativity and creativity are moving forward with great strides in every aspect. One such area is the family, and this topic is like an ocean, and one can imagine neither the beginning nor the end of it. There are so many family issues. While one is being researched, the other is waiting to be resolved. One such problem, one of the characteristics of the family theme in Uzbek literature, which has not yet been researched, was studied and illuminated.

Keywords: family, problem, solution, Uzbek literature, comparative research, common theoretical laws between literatures, scientific basis, society, philosophical-aesthetic aspects, healthy socio-cultural environment, healthy way of thinking, and healthy education system.

The socio-economic development of society and the family has accelerated to an unprecedented level. By this, creativity and creativity are moving forward with great strides on all fronts. One such area is the family, and this topic is like an ocean, and one can imagine neither the beginning nor the end of it. There are so many family issues. While one is being researched, the other is waiting to be resolved. One such problem is that the research on the family theme in Uzbek literature is waiting for its solution. Several conferences devoted to this topic are being held, monographs are being written, research is being conducted, and dissertations are being defended. However, the comparative study of the family theme in Uzbek literature has not yet been carried out. G. Hallieva says about comparative research: "In any comparative research common and unique aspects of literary phenomena are determined. This serves as a basis for the emergence of general theoretical laws in the literature. President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev says: "in today's rapidly changing conflict period, it is difficult to find answers to many complex questions in social life without a deep study of family issues on a scientific basis." From this point of view, it is important to develop a healthy socio-cultural environment, a healthy way of thinking, and a healthy education system in society. It is an objective necessity to research the philosophical and aesthetic aspects of the formation of a healthy and prosperous lifestyle in the family, increasing the role of the family in society.

Currently, we will focus on dissertations created on the topic of family research in Uzbek literature.

Yunusova Go'zal Sultonovna in her Ph.D. thesis entitled "The influence of the mother's personality on children's social perceptions in complete and incomplete families" under the conditions Uzbekistan under the influence of the Mother's personality in the Environment of complete and incomplete families Scientific and practical recommendations have been developed to determine the socio-psychological features of the students' relationship to life values, the vision of the future and their goals, and their development.

Mirakbarova Dildora Miralisher's daughter, in her Ph.D. thesis on the topic "Balance of religiosity and secularism in the strengthening of the family institution", socio-philosophical features of the strength of the family institution were analyzed based on the balance of secular and religious knowledge.

Zaretdinova Nesibeli Kurbanbaevna's Ph.D. abstract in sociology entitled "Regulation of the career choice of young people in the family by the sociometric method (in the case of the Republic of Karakalpakstan)" focuses on the career choice of young people, ensuring quality education and professional choice in achieving social maturity, supporting young people in getting a permanent job, family orientation to values in maintaining a balance between relationships and professional life, the influence of the social capital factor on the professional choice of young people, their income, employment, professional training in young people, the development of professional motivation in young professionals, improving the level of social security, personal development opportunities, the need to further improve psychological and pedagogical advice ideas are put forward.

In Fitrat's work "Family", while the characteristics of the family are partially shared with the definitions given in the dictionaries, Fitrat's philosophical thoughts about the family can be found only for him. The work discusses the reform of family life, and the writer looks for ways of salvation. The basis of Fitrat's views on the family is the thoughts and ideas presented in the Qur'an on this issue. The family, in Fitrat's interpretation, consists of three important components.

- 1) Husband.
- 2) Wife.
- 3) Children.

It is impossible to reform society and direct its development towards development without properly building the family foundation and educating the young generation on the right

path. Ultimately, the fate of a nation depends on the state of its family. Expressing such an idea in the work of Fitrat, he gives evidence: "The happiness and honor of every nation depends on its internal discipline and harmony. Peace and harmony rest on the discipline of the families of this nation. Where the family relationship is based on strong discipline, the country and the nation will be strong and great."

These thoughts show that Fitrat can foresee the future. After all, what our modern age demands from the family, Fitrat showed these demands. It should be noted that all the comments in the above-mentioned dictionaries refer to "the house and all the people living in it". In our opinion, not only a couple and their children but also a father-in-law, mother-in-law, uncles, aunts, and their children can live in one house. His work is devoted to the emergence of the family, its role and importance in society, and the internal rules and regulations that are followed in the family. In particular, in the parts of the work "On marrying or not marrying", "On wealth (money) and how a wedding should be", "On how a couple should live", and "Family life and office", these issues are discussed in detail.

President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his speech to the participants of the International Conference dedicated to the study of the heritage of the ancients, "We set a strategic task to create a new Renaissance foundation in our country in order to realize the sacred dreams of our enlightened grandfathers." For this purpose, we are carrying out fundamental reforms in the fields of science, education, and culture. In this regard, first of all, we are giving priority to organizing the educational system based on the requirements of the times, strengthening the role and influence of teachers and trainers in the life of our society. The intelligence, will, and fortitude of our progressive ancestors will serve as a model school for all of us in raising our children as people who are well-rounded, and loyal to national and universal values.

Najmidinova K.U. In his monograph "The role of national and universal moral culture in family education", on the one hand, he describes the formation of social-political, economic-spiritual paradigms specific to the development of society, and on the other hand, the new harmony of relations between social layers is being decided in society, which means that family and family relations are national and expresses his attitude about the situation, saying that it requires development based on universal moral values. The scientist strengthens his opinion with what I.A. Karimov said. According to this opinion: "The role and influence of the family is incomparable in the formation and promotion of the unique spirituality of any nation." Because the purest and purest feelings of a person, the first concepts and imaginations of life are first

formed in the bosom of the family. It is natural that the foundation of the spiritual standards and views that define the child's character, nature, and worldview - the foundations of such sacred concepts as goodness and goodness, nobility and kindness, honor and respect - are settled in the family environment. That is why the respect for parents that appears in the family environment, and the deep understanding of the duty of lifelong indebtedness to them is the basis of human qualities and family relations, the spiritual world of the family.

In this article, general information was given on the opinions expressed about the family, written monographs, and dissertations. Concluding them, we took as an example to study issues that are not the object of research

So it turned out that:

1. The family theme is as endless as the ocean.
- 2 As you research this topic, its secrets will be revealed.
3. This topic is like an ocean, it has no beginning and no end.
4. There are countless family problems, one of which is researched and the other is waiting to be solved. So, this topic will always be relevant.

Literature

- ¹ Халлиева Г. Қиёсий адабиётшунослик.–Тошкент.”Академнашр”, 2020 –Б.3
2. Мирзиёев Ш.М. . Оила ва жамият устунлиги, ҳаётимизнинг қайси ва қўрқини // Халқимизнинг розилиги бизнинг фаолиятимизга берилган энг олий баҳодир. 2-жилд. -Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2018–Б.464.
- 3 Yunusova Go‘zal Sultonovna. “То‘лиқ ва noto‘лиқ oilalardagi ona shaxsining farzand ijtimoiy tasavvurlariga ta‘sir”. диссертация PhD/–2023.–. <https://oak.uz> > pages oak.uz
- 4.Мирақбарова Дилдора Миралишер қизи “Оила институтини мустахкамлашда динийлик ва дунёвийлик мувозанати”мавзусидаги PhD диссертацияси.–2023.– <https://www.google.com/search>
- 5 Заретдинова Несибели Курбанбаевна. “Оиладаги ёшларнинг касб танлашини социометрия усули билан тартибга солиш (Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси мисолида)”. PhD автореферати –2023.– <https://www.google.com/search>
- 6 Abdurauf Fitrat. Oila | Xurshid Davron kutubxonasi.– kh-davron.uz <https://kh-davron.uz> > abdur..
7. Мирзиёев Ш.“Халқаро конференция иштирокчиларига”. WWW.prezident.uz

8. Нажмидинова К. У. “Оила тарбиясида миллий ва умуминсоний ахлоқий маданиятнинг ўрни” ,монография.-Т.; «Адолат» нашриёти, 2016 й.,Б. 224
9. Каримов И.А... Юксак маънавият – енгилмас куч. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 2008.Б. 52–53.

